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An Overview on Exploring Physiotherapy as an Adjunctive Treatment (Non-Pharmacological) for Bulimia and Anorexia Nervosa

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ABSTRACT

Background: Eating disorders (EDs) are defined by preoccupations with food, weight, and body shape, along with behaviours such as repeated episodes of excessive eating, unhealthy methods of weight control, and restricted eating. Anorexia Nervosa and Bulimia Nervosa, both clinical eating disorders, ranked as the 10th most prevalent causes of impairment among young people, with anorexia nervosa having the greatest fatality rate, and are recognized as potentially fatal conditions. The objective of this systematic review is to synthesize current understanding of efficacy, obstacles and outlining the specific goals of physiotherapy interventions for adolescents, in their physical and mental recovery process. **Methodology:** PRISMA guidelines were followed for this review. PubMed, PeDro, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar were databases used for review. The search method was initiated in January 2013 and was last modified in December 2023 Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) phrases were utilized with free terms. The present review began by identifying 54 records from 4 databases: 8 from Google Scholar, 37 from PubMed, and 5 from the Cochrane Library. After removing 12 duplicate records, 45 records were screened. 30 records were excluded, based on the mental health-based evaluation and management criteria. 15 reports were sought for retrieval, out of which 5 were not retrieved. The remaining 10 reports were assessed for eligibility, excluding 5 due to reasons such as being older than 10 years or lacking full text availability. Finally, 5 studies were included in the review, ensuring a thorough and unbiased selection process through the identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and final inclusion stages. **Conclusion:** It has been concluded that physiotherapy such as Aerobic exercises, Resistance training, Strength training, Cognitive Behavioural Therapy, Relaxation therapy plays a crucial role in improving eating disorders and physical therapy, if given along with psychological sessions provides a better outcome for patients eating disorders.

Keywords: Anorexia Nervosa, Bulimia Nervosa, Eating Disorder, Physical Therapy, Physiotherapy

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Introduction

Eating disorders (EDs) are defined by preoccupations with food, weight, and body shape, along with behaviours such as repeated episodes of excessive eating, unhealthy methods of weight control, and restricted eating. These disorders lead to diminished physical and mental well-being, reduced quality of life, and impaired social functioning. EDs are frequently accompanied by cardiovascular deconditioning, compromised bone health, and muscle frailty in adolescents.¹ They are recognized as potentially fatal conditions and rank as the 10th most prevalent causes of impairment among young people, with Anorexia nervosa (AN) having the greatest fatality rate. Anorexia nervosa is a baffling and terrible condition that primarily affects young women. It involves intentional starvation to the point of extreme thinness, which poses a serious risk to the individual's life. Women diagnosed with Anorexia nervosa face a much higher risk of premature death, with a 6-12 times greater likelihood compared to the general population².

It is marked by a deliberate reluctance to maintain a healthy body weight, a strong aversion to gaining weight, a lack of recognition of the severity of being underweight, and disruptions in perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs about one's own body (i.e., body image). It is linked to significant physical and psychological morbidity, which includes medical issues connected with extreme underweight, anxiety, depression, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress. AN has also been associated with a proclivity to repress negative emotions and ideas as affected individuals strive to evade interpersonal conflicts. The onset of this condition usually manifests throughout adolescence or early adulthood, with the highest prevalence rates observed in girls aged 15 to 25 years. Due to the unresolved nature of the condition and the lack of consensus on appropriate treatment methods, AN is linked to a bleak prognosis and high rates of relapse³.

Eating Disorders (EDs) represent a significant public health concern, particularly among adolescents. These complex psychiatric illnesses not only impact psychological well-being but also manifest physically, affecting various organ systems. In recent years, the role of physiotherapy in the multidisciplinary treatment of eating disorders has gained recognition, offering a holistic approach to address both the mental and physical aspects of these conditions.

There are other EDs like Binge-eating disorder (BED) and Bulimia nervosa (BN) which are characterized by repeated bouts of excessive eating. During these episodes, individuals suffer a lack of control over their eating and devour significant quantities of food. In the context of BED, individuals engage in compensatory behaviours, such as the use of laxatives or self-induced purging, in order to avoid gaining weight. This information is based on the DSM 5 criteria set forth by the American Psychiatric Association in 2013. Naturalistic research is particularly well-suited to studying binge eating due to its highly contextualized character, which involves various internal factors such as unpleasant emotions and food cravings, as well as external triggers like skipping meals. The act of consuming food as a response to bad emotions is referred to as 'emotional eating' (*Boredom Proneness and Emotion Regulation Predict Emotional Eating - Amanda C Crockett, Samantha K Myhre, Paul D Rokke, 2015, n.d.*). The affect regulation model of binge eating suggests that negative affect acts as a catalyst for binge eating, and binge eating, in turn, serves as a means to alleviate it. This model, proposed by Heatherton and Baumeister in 1991, offers an explanation for the perpetuation of binge eating behaviour. Consistent with this notion, both experimental and naturalistic paradigms indicate that bad mood can serve as a precursor to binge eating in persons diagnosed with BED⁴.

Various evidence-based clinical guidelines advocate for targeted psychosocial therapies for patients experiencing recurring episodes of binge eating. Guerdjikova et al. (2019)⁵ recommend the use of a multidisciplinary team consisting of a psychologist, a dietician, and a psychiatrist to provide support to persons who experience repeated episodes of binge eating, particularly when these episodes are accompanied by a high body mass index (BMI). Some studies recommend HAPIFED, (Healthy Approach to weight management and Food in Eating Disorders), Cognitive Behavioural Therapy Enhanced (CBT-E) with Behavioural Weight Loss Therapy (BWLT) to treat patients who have recurring episodes of binge eating and a high body mass index (BMI) (*Update on Binge Eating Disorder - PubMed, n.d.*). Their protocol consisted of four sessions conducted by nutritionists that provided psycho-education on topics such as the Famine Reaction and the reasons behind diet failures (session 3), the importance of regular eating (session 4), the distinction between healthy and unhealthy exercise (session 5, with the assistance of an occupational therapist), and healthy eating strategies for weight loss (session 7). Nevertheless, as the participants had been diagnosed with BN, a condition characterized by elevated weight and body shape anxieties as well as dietary limitations, the research team exercised caution when addressing these subjects during the sessions, aiming to prevent any exacerbation of eating disorder symptoms¹. Internationally, medical experts universally acknowledge physical activity as an essential component of a well-balanced and healthy way of living. Research has shown that engaging in physical activity has wide-ranging beneficial benefits on the psychological well-being, body image, overall quality of life, and physical and mental health of children and adolescents^{6,7}.

The primary justifications for recommending physiotherapy for AN patients are the distorted bodily experience, which encompasses perception, attitudes, and behaviour, and the compulsive and excessive physical activity commonly observed in these patients. To address the distorted bodily experience and hyperactivity commonly seen in individuals with AN, Physiotherapists are advised to select techniques, such as relaxation, breathing exercises, awareness exercises, and exercise regimens, that are tailored to the patient's specific needs⁸.

In the presence of a physiotherapist as a member of the therapy team, Davila et al. 2017 saw a notable enhancement in the psycho-pathological traits, body image, and self-reported quality of life among the patients. The researchers concluded that it is important to provide extensive mental health training to physiotherapists so that they may effectively contribute to the multidisciplinary team responsible for managing these illnesses (Vancampfort et.al, 2014)⁹.

For women with anorexia nervosa, it is recommended to engage in strength training and high intensity resistance exercises to enhance muscle strength. Additionally, including body-based art therapy (BBAT), receiving full body massages, and receiving instructions on relaxation techniques can provide support in improving eating behaviour. Furthermore, BBAT not only improves individuals' views towards their bodies, but also promotes their mood and reduces anxiety through full body massage and relaxation guidance. Engaging in stretching, isometric, endurance cardiovascular, and muscular exercises, along with incorporating exercise and compulsive exercise management into cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT), has been shown to enhance quality of life (Minano-Garrido et al., 2022)⁹.

Eating disorders like bulimia and anorexia nervosa are challenging to treat due to their complex interplay of physical and psychological symptoms, and traditional approaches often yield limited success. Physiotherapy, as a non-pharmacological intervention, has shown potential to support these patients by enhancing physical health, body awareness, and mental well-being. However, evidence on its effectiveness as an adjunctive treatment remains sparse and fragmented. This study aims to consolidate existing research on physiotherapy's role in treating these disorders, providing insights into its clinical benefits and helping to guide more integrative treatment approaches for improved patient outcomes.

Methodology

The preferred reporting items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines for the flow diagram (Chosen Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews) formed the basis for this review as represented in figure 1. The following electronic databases were explored for the review and experimental study that took place between 2013 and 2023: Search engines were Google Scholar, PubMed, PeDro, and the Cochrane library. The Studies included were RCTs, reviews done on Physiotherapy in EDs.

Figure 1 : PRISMA FLOWCHART

Types of Interventions: Eating disorders (Anorexia Nervosa and Bulimia Nervosa) were included in the systematic studies that looked at the effects of physical therapy, either alone or as part of a multi-component intervention.

Types of Studies: All systematic reviews (SRs) of main research (e.g., randomized controlled trials [RCTs]) were considered, according to Cochrane's criteria; literature reviews and surveys were also considered.

Search Strategy: The search method was initiated by the authors in January 2013 and was last modified in December 2023 to incorporate the most recent evidence from the following databases: PubMed, PeDro, Cochrane Library and Google Scholar. Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) phrases were utilized with free terms. We used PICOS framework to select articles from the databases presented in table 1.

Table -1: Search strategy - PICOS framework

Framework	Search items
Population (P)	"Eating disorders" OR "Eulimia nervosa" OR "anorexia nervosa"
Intervention (I)	Physiotherapy based interventions, such as ("aerobic exercise" OR "resistance training" OR "relaxation therapy" OR "body awareness therapy" OR "massage" OR "yoga" OR "physiotherapy" OR "physical therapy" OR "exercise therapy" OR "aerobic exercise" OR "resistance training" OR "yoga" OR "massage" OR "relaxation techniques"
Comparison (C):	"standard care" OR "pharmacological treatment" OR "psychotherapy"
Outcomes (O):	Improvement in "symptom reduction" OR "body mass index" OR "muscle strength" OR "cardiovascular fitness" OR "mental health" OR "quality of life" OR "reduced anxiety and depression symptoms" OR "muscle strength" OR "mental health" OR "quality of life"
Study Design (S):	"Systematic review" OR "randomized controlled trial" OR "RCT" OR "meta analysis" OR "co-intervention study"
("Bulimia nervosa" OR "Anorexia nervosa") AND ("Physiotherapy" OR "physical therapy" OR "exercise therapy" OR "aerobic exercise" OR "resistance training" OR "yoga" OR "massage" OR "relaxation techniques") AND ("standard care" OR "pharmacological treatment" OR "psychotherapy") AND ("improvement" OR "symptom reduction" OR "BMI increase" OR "muscle strength" OR "mental health" OR "quality of life") AND ("systematic review" OR "randomized controlled trial" OR "RCT" OR "meta analysis" OR "co-intervention study").	

Study Screening and Selection: An extensive literature search was carried out by the four researchers (KZ, RCJ, SKB and MD). Before being submitted to the Rayyan website for selection, the records that were obtained were analyzed by Zotero, which is the Corporation for Digital Scholarship project, to remove duplicates. Following that, records were screened by four separate researchers (KZ, RCJ, SKB, and MD) using the eligibility criteria applied to abstracts and titles. In order to read the complete content and decide which records were appropriate for inclusion, they were retrieved. In situations when reviewers could not agree, a fifth author (JM) was asked to help bring everyone around to the same conclusion.

Results

The results of this systematic review on physiotherapy treatments for individuals with BN and AN shed light on the dynamic nature of interdisciplinary approaches to treating eating disorders. Incorporating physiotherapy into their treatment plans has gained popularity in recent years due to the substantial impact these conditions have on the emotional and physical health of teenagers. The purpose of this debate is to examine the systematic review's main points, their ramifications, and potential future research areas

Characteristics of the study- Researchers from Australia, Spain, France, and several European collaborations conducted the studies that were part of the systematic review on physiotherapy as an adjuvant treatment for eating disorders as mentioned in table 2. While Minano-Garrido et al. (2022)¹⁰ from Spain and Toutain et al. (2022)¹¹ from France carried out systematic reviews concentrating on therapies like aerobic and resistance training for eating disorders, the Australian authors Dias RC & Machado & Ferreira (2014)¹² reviewed RCTs on physiotherapy interventions. A meta-analysis of CBT and family-based therapy for eating disorders was carried out by Monteleone et al. (2022)¹³, speaking for Europe and Australia. Finally, a narrative review of physical, nutritional, and psychosocial physiotherapy therapies was presented by Clemente-Suárez et al. (2023)¹⁴ from Spain. This global study highlights the interest in investigating the potential of physical therapy in the treatment of eating disorders. Above table

displays various treatment options available for treatment of AN and BN that includes psychosocial interventions, aerobic exercises, resistance training, relaxation therapy, massage, CBT-ED, FBT and physical activity interventions.

Table- 2: General characteristics of included review

Author, year Corresponding Country	Publication years	Type of study	Eating disorder	Type of treatment	Findings on behalf of physical therapy treatment
Machado & Ferreira, 2014; Australia – Sydney	Till February 2013	Systematic review of RCTs	Anorexia Nervosa & Bulimia Nervosa	Aerobic exercise, Resistance training, Relaxation therapy Massage Basic body awareness, Yoga	Effective in reducing eating disorder outcome, body mass index, body fat percentage, depression and anxiety symptoms
Minano-Garrido et al., 2022; Europe-Spain	Till December 2020	Systematic review, RCT, co-intervention studies	Anorexia Nervosa & Bulimia Nervosa	Strength training High intensity resistance training	Quality of life improves, Increased endurance, cardio-vascular capacity and muscle strength
Monteleone et al., 2022 Europe-Australia	Till December 2021	Systematic meta review & meta analysis of RCTs	Anorexia Nervosa, Bulimia Nervosa & Binge eating disorder	FBT- Family based therapy CBT-ED- individual cognitive behaviour therapy	FBT effective in Anorexia Nervosa & Bulimia Nervosa in Adolescents CBT-ED effective in Bulimia Nervosa in adults FBT & CBT-ED-combined worried for Binge eating disorder
Toutain et al., 2022; Europe-France	Till November 2021	Systematic review of RCTs	Anorexia Nervosa	Aerobic exercise Resistance training	Physical exercise reduces symptoms of anorexia and mental health, also improve muscle strength Helps in improving weight gain
Clemente-Suárez et al., 2023; Europe-Spain	2012 to 2023	Narrative review	Anorexia Nervosa & Bulimia Nervosa	Physical activity interventions Nutritional interventions, Psycho-social interventions Physical therapy intervention-relaxation, massage, breathing exercise and therapeutic exercise	Improves anorexia symptomatology, induce relaxation and release pain

The present review also provide an insight how these treatment has benefitted the individual and improves the physical and mental health, quality of life, helps in weight gain , reduces pain and induces relaxation.

1. The Impact of Physical Therapy on Patients: This review delves at the physiological impacts on EDs and the ways in which physical therapy interventions can provide relief. Reducing the impacts of cardiovascular deconditioning, decreased bone health, and weak muscles has been shown to be possible with a range of treatments, including physical conditioning, manual therapy, and exercise prescription.

Treatments such as therapeutic aerobic exercise, massage, basic body awareness therapy, and yoga, which are all part of supervised physical therapy, may help patients with AN and BN gain weight and improve their general health. Patients suffering from EDs may find that basic body awareness therapy, aerobic exercise, and yoga all contribute to a better overall quality of life. Refeeding patients with AN should be safe and advantageous for restoring body composition and bone mineral density, mood, and anxiety, according to current information (Minano-Garrido et al., 2022)¹⁵. Managed physical activity has no negative effects on weight growth, has no correlation with eating disorders, and really has favourable effects on both mental and physical health (Moola et al., 2013)¹⁶.

Strategies for Physical Therapy Anorexia treatment recommendations include a multi-pronged intervention program that includes physiotherapy to address the patient's skewed body image through behavioural, attitude, and perception-based therapies. The subject has already been covered, but physical treatment can also add to the reported excessive exercise.

Physiotherapy offers a variety of therapeutic strategies that can be used to help people with AN achieve their therapy goals. They work equally well when used alone or in a small group. Because of the correlation between the severity and length of time spent suffering from an eating problem and the likelihood of describing lower back discomfort, postural exercises are one of the suggested approaches to treatment. Low muscle tone and weakness cause postural compensations (such as scoliosis) and lower back pain, which manifests in patients with long-term AN. Hence, to increase self-esteem and decrease postural abnormalities, strength training—particularly core exercises—and postural control and stability activities might help strengthen hypotonic muscles. Physiotherapy for anorexia also includes stretching exercises to bring the tone of hypertonic muscles back to normal. There is some evidence that these low-intensity activities can enhance health markers and quality of life without affecting weight or body mass index recovery, which is a good sign. In addition, a recent study replicated these results by combining weight training with stretching, with the latter being done after the training session had concluded. The researchers focused on the main muscles. Furthermore, research on anorexia patients has shown that massage can alleviate a number of symptoms related to the illness. In particular, the stress hormone cortisol is decreased and anxiety and stress levels are reduced with massage. In addition, massage alleviates a sense of body dissatisfaction. The primary processes that account for massage's beneficial benefits include an increase in parasympathetic arousal (caused by the catecholamine and cortisol decreasing after the massage), a rise in vagal tone, and a greater stimulation of the feel-good neurotransmitters serotonin and dopamine. For an even more soothing experience, techniques like patting, light stroking, kneading, and passive mobilization of the arms and legs have been tried. Furthermore, the most typical massage technique for anorexic patients is a calming and stimulating leg or back massage. Anorexia sufferers who want to alleviate their symptoms could try acupuncture, relaxation techniques, or both. These methods help lower stress and anxiety levels (both perceived and cortisol). Physiotherapists can help patients with eating disorders by selecting the most appropriate technique from a list of proven methods. These methods include yoga, mindfulness, biofeedback, autogenic training, and Jacobson's progressive relaxation. The selection process is based on the patient's current stage of the disorder, its severity, and other factors. If you want to lower your breath frequency while simultaneously increasing the amplitude of your abdominal respiration and lengthening the duration of your expiration phase, you can combine the relaxation exercises with breathing exercises. According to Clemente-Suárez et al. (2023)¹⁴, patients with anorexia nervosa report better breath control and body image as a result of these breathing exercises.

2. **A Comprehensive Method of Care:** A significant finding is the recognition of physiotherapy as a vital component of the multidisciplinary approach. Problems with many bodily systems and mental health disorders are common with AN. The comprehensive nature of physiotherapy is an essential component of the care needed for a speedy recovery. Incorporating exercise into the treatment plan requires attention to five key areas. According to (Quesnel et al., 2018)¹⁷, these factors encompass physiological stability, the rate of weight restoration, the ability to adhere to a nutrition program, one's psychological profile in relation to exercise, and one's exercise history and objectives.

For a complete recovery, it is crucial to have a realistic and positive body image. Patients should be cognizant of this condition and maintain a non-judgmental focus on the present moment because it is a natural part of gaining weight and experiencing physical changes (Kolnes, 2012)¹⁸ Therefore, treatment cannot proceed without first facilitating the development of a healthy self-image and the acceptance of one's own emotions and needs (Probst et al. 2013)⁷. The therapy aims at more than just physical therapy exercises; it also places a premium on the patient's emotional and experiential healing. Although it may be challenging for the patient, it is a means to connect with their inner world by stepping out of their comfort zone and confronting new opportunities, emotions (such as fear, guilt, or wrath), or thoughts. This requires the physiotherapist to facilitate a risk-free setting and provide direction to patients as they work through treatment (Probst and Diedens 2017)¹⁹. Teaching patient safe and healthy ways to exercise is another crucial component (Moola et al. 2013)¹⁶.

3. **Programs Tailored to Teen Involvement:** Treatment plans must take into consideration the unique physiological and developmental aspects of puberty. The systematic review highlights the importance of tailoring physiotherapy treatments to the specific needs of this age group in order to achieve the best possible outcomes from treatment. The evaluation and continuous treatment of EDs in teenagers seem to be best accomplished by an interdisciplinary team of experts from the fields of medicine, nursing, nutrition, and mental health, due to the complexity of the bio-psychosocial components of these illnesses. As supplementary treatments, physical and occupational therapy could be beneficial. Professionals in the medical

field caring for teenagers and their families should have extensive background in the treatment of EDs. They ought to be well-versed on the emotional and physical changes that typically occur during adolescence. EDs are complicated, long-term health problems necessitate examination and therapy that takes these aspects into account. The ideal way to do an assessment and maintain treatment is with a multidisciplinary team that includes experts in medicine, nursing, nutrition, and mental health. Medical professionals treating with eating disorders should be well-versed in both the unique challenges faced by this age group and the typical physical and mental changes that occur during this time. Malnutrition, clinical signs of physical or mental decompensation, or the ineffectiveness of out-patient treatment all indicate that an individual with an eating disorder should be hospitalized. The treatment should be administered regularly, with the right amount of force, and for the right amount of time ('Eating Disorders in Adolescents', 1998).

Framework for Clinical Application:

1. Including Physical Therapy in Treatment Plans:

BN and AN should receive physiotherapy as part of their normal treatment regimens, according to the literature reviewed. Physiotherapy should be seen by clinicians and healthcare providers as an essential part of the interdisciplinary treatment plan for these patients.

Postural exercises: As a result of muscle weakness, people with AN often appear stooped. As a rule, you'll notice your shoulders pulling back, your trapezius muscles clenched, and your pelvis tilted forward (Kolnes 2012)¹⁸. The main goals of therapy should be to alleviate muscle tension, improve postural stability and muscle strength, and correct muscle imbalances (Monteleone et al., 2023)¹³. In addition to facilitating healthy breathing, good posture influences self-esteem.

Relaxation exercises: It promotes calmness and self-awareness. According to Probst and Diedens (2017)¹⁹, relaxation techniques can help reduce tension and anxiety. Clear thinking and increased self-awareness are two additional benefits of relaxation (Probst 2013)¹⁹. According to (Pavlova et al., 2010)²⁰ doing relaxation activities consistently, preferably twice weekly, is crucial. A variety of methods may be provided to the patients. A popular method that requires focus and isn't just passive is Jacobson's progressive relaxation, often known as Progressive Muscle Relaxation, or PMR (Probst et al. 2013)⁷. A more progressive approach was taken in its design for striated muscles (Gilbert, 2014)²¹ (Clemente-Suárez et al., 2023)¹⁴. Being cognizant of the distinction between fully relaxed and fully engaged muscles is the goal. According to (Pavlova et al., 2010)²⁰ we gradually work on every area of the body, reducing tension in the muscles and allowing them to relax.

Autogenic training, developed by Schultz, is "a mental exercise focused on various sensations of physical relaxation" (Kwekkeboom & Gretarsdottir, 2006)⁶. The emphasis is once again on the distinction between relaxed and tense muscles. As stated by (Pavlova et al., 2010)²⁰, the goal is to induce muscular relaxation by means of sensations of weightlessness and warmth in the limbs, in conjunction with regular breathing.

Mindfulness or sensory awareness training: Training in mindfulness or sensory awareness entails bringing one's non-judgmental, non-threatening attention to one's internal bodily experience in the here and now (Schuman-Olivier et al., 2020)²¹. The ability to identify one's emotions and the relationship between one's feelings and bodily sensations are both impacted by our level of awareness of our inner lives. Practicing mindfulness (Soundy et al., 2016)²³ defined a body scan as "a focused exploration of inner body parts and sensations," including respiration, heartbeat, and exhaustion. When the focus area becomes less active, it follows. Mateos Rodríguez et al., (2014)²⁴ expected that mindfulness activities can help with obsessive thoughts about food, weight, and shape, as well as with reduced interoceptive awareness and stubborn thinking.

Mirror Exercises: The purpose of mirror exercises is to improve one's view of oneself (Probst et al. 2013)⁶. Patients suffering from AN often place a high value on mirrors (Probst and Diedens et al, 2017)¹⁹. According to Probst et al. (2013)⁶, there are three ways people interact with mirrors: regularly, avoidant (without looking), or constantly. Because they are critical of themselves and their appearance, patients with AN often avoid looking in mirrors. This further supports the idea that early treatment should not involve mirror exercises (Kolnes et al. 2012)¹⁸. According to (Probst et al., 2008)⁷, this practice can assist patients in developing a realistic self-image and learning to embrace their changing bodies. The goal of this exercise is to visually inspect your body without passing judgment and focusing on troublesome areas in particular.

Feldenkrais method: Awareness via movement is another name for the Feldenkrais method, and it sums up the approach perfectly. The founder, Moshe Feldenkrais, once stated that our actions mirror our internal self-perception. What he meant was that when we train ourselves to be more self-aware, we also train ourselves to be more conscious of our habits, our daily routines, and whether we're in a relaxed or tense state of mind. In most cases, this approach heightens our emotional awareness and sensitivity. That allows us to experience life to the fullest and identify our essential. By bringing the body and mind into harmony with its function, the exercise seeks to promote self-awareness through movement (Fonow et al., 2016.)²⁵. Patients with AN who have an unhealthy relationship with their body can also benefit from the Feldenkrais method. By introducing them to their bodies through various means (perceiving, moving, and touching), these lessons help patients feel more comfortable and at ease. Despite this, Feldenkrais "showed improvements referring to the feeling of helplessness against demands from the outside, inner emptiness, restlessness and inferiority," according to (Laumer et al., 2004)²⁶.

Breathing exercises: Practicing deep breathing, a wonderful approach to become more attuned to one's body is to practice breathing exercises. Reducing the patient's respiratory frequency and promoting relaxation are two benefits of conscious breathing. Because patients with AN often breathe primarily into their chests due to fear of bloating, our focus with them is on incorporating the abdominal breathing pattern and lengthening expiration (Probst et al. 2013; Pavlova 2010)^{7, 20}. All respiratory motion is reduced, and the breathing cycle is shortened. Additionally, the vast majority of patients report complete and utter lack of awareness of their breathing (Kolnes 2012)¹⁸. As with most relaxation techniques, we can incorporate breathing exercises into our routine or practice contact breathing on its own. The therapist puts his hands on the patient's belly (or a book or a ball if the patient can't handle direct touch) and instructs them to breathe in through their fingers while concentrating on diaphragmatic and belly activation (Pavlova 2010)²⁰.

Massage and Soft tissue techniques: It can be done in conjunction with passive mobilizations, in which the therapist gently moves the patient's limbs. According to Probst et al. (2013)⁷, it is expected to promote relaxation and increase bodily awareness. Some of the massage techniques include kneading, light stroking, and patting. Massages can alleviate anxiety and are an excellent first step in treating patients with extremely low body mass index (Pavlova 2010; Moraska et al., 2010)^{20, 27}.

2. Healthcare Professionals Working Together:

The results highlight the significance of teamwork among various medical specialists, such as dietitians, physiotherapists, psychologists, and psychiatrists. Treatment paradigms for eating disorders should be more comprehensive and successful with a united and collaborative effort. Physical therapy, which focuses on physical activity, body experience, and insight, may be an effective treatment option for EDs. Patients with distorted body images and unhealthy physical activity behaviours view improving their self-esteem and body image as key components of their treatment plans.

Because of the complex nature of EDs, a multidisciplinary group of experts in medicine, psychology, and nutrition must work together to treat these conditions. For the purpose of medical nutrition therapy, which aims to normalize eating patterns and nutritional status, the Registered Dietician (RD) plays a crucial role as a member of the treatment team. Nutritional therapists (RDs) play an essential role in the treatment of eating disorders by providing nutritional counseling, identifying clinical symptoms, and aiding with medical monitoring, all while keeping in mind the importance of psychotherapy and medicines. To help RDs become more knowledgeable in the area of eating disorders, there are specialized materials available to them. In order to enhance treatment results for eating disorders and identify effective main and secondary therapies, more evidence-based research is needed (American Dietetic Association, 2006).

Psychological therapies

Trans-diagnostic Cognitive Behaviour Therapy - Enhanced (CBT-E) is the primary treatment for eating disorders, resulting in significant symptom reduction and improved results. This is typically administered in 20 weekly sessions for bulimia nervosa and BED, and 40 sessions for anorexia nervosa. Recent breakthroughs in treating eating disorders include psychological therapy trials for anorexia nervosa in children, adolescents, and adults, supported by systematic reviews and meta-analyses. In children and adolescents, a theoretical family-based treatment (FBT) is the primary mode of care. FBT can be provided in both complete and divided families. Family therapy has also been used to treat BN. A modified version of CBT-E with additional brief

family sessions offers a poorer evidence foundation than FBT. Similarly, adolescent focused psychotherapy can help younger people with anorexia nervosa (Hay, 2020)¹.

Other evidence-based psychological therapies for anorexia nervosa include Maudsley Anorexia Nervosa Therapy for Adults (MANTRA), Specialist Supportive Clinical Management (SSCM), and Focal Psychodynamic Therapy (FPT). All therapies involve psycho-education and try to restore the person's physical health through weight monitoring, nutritional counselling, and meal planning, which are frequently combined with sessions with a trained dietician. They were designed for personalized outpatient care lasting 8 months or more. CBT has been developed for group delivery, as is common in hospital programmes. All have manuals that provide direction for therapies and are utilized throughout training. In Australia, CBT is the most available training option, followed by SSCM and MANTRA. All have moderate rates of attrition (Hay, 2020)¹.

Yoga: As an adjunct to physical therapy, yoga poses may be prescribed. It connects the physical postures (asanas), breathing techniques (pranayamas), and meditation (dhyanas) of yoga (Ostermann, Vogel, Boehm, et al., 2019)²⁸. All things considered, it is thought to be an excellent method for enhancing self-awareness and –soothing (Douglass, 2009)²⁹, particularly the inwardly focused Hatha yoga, which boosts self-esteem (O'Shea et al 2022). Ostermann, Vogel, Starke, et al., (2019)²⁸ found that regular yoga practice can help people relax and get in touch with their emotions. Also, anxiety, despair, and concerns about one's weight and shape can be alleviated via regular yoga practice, as studies have demonstrated that this practice lowers cortisol levels while increasing GABA and dopamine levels (Douglass 2009²⁹; Hall et al. 2016)³⁰. The impact of yoga on food obsession is another advantage of incorporating it into the treatment plan. According to (Carei et al., 2010)³¹, this exercise can help patients reduce thoughts of food preoccupation, hence it's recommended to do it before or after meals.

Dance: When it comes to influencing body image and self-acceptance, dance is only one more medium (Krueger and Schofield 1986)³². According to Ravelin et al. (2006)³³, this form of movement therapy allows patients to express themselves via dance. Because of this intervention, we are able to overcome patients' inhibitions and let them express themselves more freely. According to (Padrão et al., 2013)³⁴, reawakening them and demonstrating that they may depend on their bodies and parts is crucial because they are somewhat confined by their own inflated self-perception. Dancing relieves mental and physical stress, which in turn reduces anxiety and depression, two additional symptoms of AN (Ravelin et al. 2006)³³. We can also invite the patient to join the group dance session after he starts to feel better about himself. They are able to express their feelings and act more impulsively when they are together (Tavormina & Tavormina, 2018)³⁵. On top of that, it's a means of communication. Patients may find that dancing helps they communicate themselves more effectively than words alone. Experiences are evoked differently by various genres. Group dance sessions offer social interaction and a means of nonverbal communication; jazz or ballet, with its precise framework, can help patients concentrate; and improvised or contemporary dance can lead to the development of creativity (Ravelin et al. 2006)³³.

Tai chi: It is a martial art and traditional Chinese method of self-defence that emphasizes the harmony between the body and the mind. Relaxation, gentle and graceful movement and postures, deep belly breathing, and meditation are all part of it (Probst, 2013)⁷. Although there is a lack of evidence linking Tai chi directly to improved outcomes for AN patients, the numerous health advantages of the practice can bolster existing treatments. A modest exercise intervention impacts cardiorespiratory and musculoskeletal function (Li et al., 2001)³⁶. This mind-body technique also decreases osteopenia (Tong et al., 2018)³⁷.

Physical activity and recreation: Over exercising is sometimes motivated by patients' dissatisfaction with their physical appearance. People with eating disorders often engage in excessive physical activity in an effort to shed pounds and improve their appearance. For a long time, fitness exercises and sports games were not allowed as part of treatment due to this pathologic behaviour. Nevertheless, new research suggests that patients may also benefit from exercise regimens that are both controlled and well monitored by their physiotherapists. Aerobics, calisthenics, athletics, gymnastics, resistance training, and fitness are common interventions. The level of strength and density of bone are affected by these treatments. During the process, it is important to monitor the patient's heart rate, movement intensity, and any other subjective impressions. Physiotherapy sessions like this are thought to aid in the following ways: decreasing covert physical activities; educating patients on the proper amount and frequency

of physical activity; and providing patients with an opportunity to cope with the noticeable changes occurring inside their bodies (Probst et al. 2013)⁷.

Discussion

The present review shows a couple of studies that have been carried out with the prospects of Physiotherapy in AN and BN which are mental health disorders. The results show that there is a huge scope of research to be carried out in Physiotherapy for EDs. The study highlights the changing methods used to tackle eating problems in teenagers, with a particular emphasis on the involvement of physiotherapy. The results underscore the crucial significance of physiotherapy in the treatment of individuals suffering from anorexia nervosa (AN) and bulimia nervosa (BN), revealing its beneficial influence on both the physical and mental well-being of individuals. The primary crucial point is the significant physiological advantages of including physiotherapy in treatment strategies. Interventions such as therapeutic aerobic exercise, massage, body awareness therapy, and yoga have demonstrated potential in improving the overall well-being of people with eating disorders by treating cardiovascular deconditioning, strengthening bone health, and increasing muscle strength. Significantly, these methods not only lead to an increase in body weight but also result in enhancements in emotional state, levels of anxiety, and physical structure.

Another essential component emphasized is the all-encompassing scope of care that physiotherapy provides. In addition to physical activities, the review emphasizes the significance of developing a pragmatic and optimistic perception of one's body, recognizing the emotional and experiential aspects of the healing process. Physiotherapists have the responsibility of leading patients in secure environments, instructing them on exercises that are both safe and beneficial for their health, and playing a vital part in the multidisciplinary team with dietitians, psychologists, and psychiatrists. Moreover, the research emphasizes the necessity of customized physiotherapy programs that take into account the distinct physiological and developmental characteristics of adolescents. The text underscores the significance of multidisciplinary teamwork, wherein healthcare specialists from many professions cooperate to deliver comprehensive care. According to the review, incorporating physiotherapy is crucial for attaining favourable treatment results in teenagers with eating problems (Monteleone et al, 2023)¹³.

The clinical application framework integrates the prescribed physiotherapy procedures, such as postural exercises, relaxation techniques, mindfulness, and breathing exercises. The focus lies in customizing these therapies to cater to the specific requirements of individuals with AN and BN. The comprehensive method outlined in this article not only focuses on physical issues but also strives to improve self-awareness, body image, and total mental well-being (Moola et al, 2013)¹⁶. Ultimately, this comprehensive analysis offers significant perspectives on the contribution of physiotherapy in the therapeutic approach to eating disorders in individuals. To achieve enhanced and holistic strategies for addressing the intricate interaction of psychological and physiological factors in eating disorders, we should acknowledge its effectiveness, incorporate it into treatment protocols, foster collaboration among healthcare professionals, and advocate for additional research (Clemente-Suárez et al, 2023)¹⁴.

Overall, the systematic analysis provides significant insights into the continuing discussion around multidisciplinary care for individuals with eating disorders who are receiving physiotherapy treatment. Crucial stages in developing the field of physiotherapy include acknowledging the efficacy of these therapies, incorporating them into treatment protocols, encouraging healthcare professionals to work together, and pushing for additional research. Improved treatment approaches that take into account the psychological and physiological aspects of eating disorders in teenagers are possible according to the results of this comprehensive review.

Limitations: The study was limited to including research in English language only. Since EDs are considered to be more prevalent in the Western world, the studies in other languages could be included. The studies that were included were from Europe and Australia only.

Future scope: The field of exercise and eating disorder is less-investigated and there are few existing studies available. Quasi-experimental designs and RCTs with insufficient power and insufficient description of blinding and randomization procedures are the key characteristics of the research that is currently available. In the future, it is essential that well-designed RCTs be created. Researchers and medical professionals will be able to make more definitive comments about the effects of adding activity into treatment with the help of well-conducted experimental studies. Future researchers might find it useful to acknowledge the contributions made by the qualitative paradigm to our growing understanding of

exercise in AN. Numerous fresh perspectives on how patients perceive exercise have been revealed by qualitative study. For example, this study has shown that although the current approach to treating AN is "concentric," meaning it aims to control the condition at the level of actions and emotions, people with AN also benefit from body-based therapies. This discovery reminds academics that treating anorexia requires treating the anorexic body as a whole, as it is essentially a somatic and psychological condition. In addition, individuals suffering from AN are referred to as disembodied, as they frequently lack a connection to physical sensations like hunger, pain, or cold. It is crucial that they gain from body-based therapies that educate them about embodied experiences because of this. According to this research, involving patients in activities during therapy promotes a sense of re-embodiment and aids in their re-engagement with their bodies. Additionally, the advantages of action in developing a new, non-anorexic identity have been highlighted by qualitative research, which has also highlighted patients' preferences for exercise while undergoing therapy. For example, research has shown that, while exercise is a good diversion from negative attention to the body, "boring" exercise regimens or regimens that resemble training can exacerbate negative bodily concentration and produce discomfort. Therefore, qualitative research is essential for guiding the development of interventions as well as for better understanding the experience of AN and exercise (Moola et al, 2013)¹⁶.

Clinical Implication: Clinical implication of this study is to show that there is ample scope of research to be carried out in the field of Physiotherapy for EDs 9 mental disorders. The research provides a cluster all physiotherapy treatment for treating eating disorders. The study helps us to understand, the I measures which can be taken by medical practitioners and encourage patients with eating disorders to exercises in an appropriate way under the expert supervision. It also broader the treatment aspects foe patients with eating disorders.

Conclusion

This systematic review highlights the changing methods used to tackle eating problems in teenagers, with a particular emphasis on the involvement of physiotherapy. The results underscore the crucial significance of physiotherapy in the treatment of individuals suffering from anorexia nervosa (AN) and bulimia nervosa (BN), revealing its beneficial influence on both the physical and mental well-being of individuals. The primary crucial point is the significant physiological advantages of include physiotherapy in treatment strategies. Interventions such as therapeutic aerobic exercise, massage, body awareness therapy, and yoga have demonstrated potential in improving the overall well-being of people with eating disorders by treating cardiovascular deconditioning, strengthening bone health, and increasing muscle strength. Significantly, these methods not only lead to an increase in body weight but also result in enhancements in emotional state, levels of anxiety, and physical structure.

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Ethical Consideration: No ethical consideration was required for this study.

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